

Ruthenium-triphenylphosphine complex with pendent quinolyl Schiff base ligand : Synthesis, spectral characterization and catalytic property[†]

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Abstract : The *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (1) (where, PMAQ = 8-{(2'-pyridylmethylene)amino}quinoline) complex has been synthesized and characterized by several spectroscopic techniques. The absorption and emission properties of the complex have been studied. Upon excitation in ILCT band at 331 nm, the complex exhibits emission at 475 nm. The emission decay profile has bi-exponential in nature with life time of 3.98 ns. The complex exhibits a quasi-reversible one electron Ru^{II}/Ru^{III} oxidation couple along with a ligand based reduction in cyclic voltammetric study. The redox properties are well supported by DFT data. The electronic structure of the complex has been interpreted by DFT method. The spin allowed electronic transitions computed by TDDFT method have a good agreement with the experimental spectrum of the complex. The complex efficiently catalyzes the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to the respective aldehydes and ketones with moderate to high conversions in presence of N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMO) as co-oxidant.

Keywords : Ruthenium triphenylphosphine complex, Schiff base ligand, electrochemistry, catalytic oxidation reaction, DFT calculation.

Introduction

The transition metal complexes with π -acidic diimine (-N=C-C=N-) functional polypyridyl compounds show exciting photochemical and photophysical properties, and have applications in many technological fields¹. The excited states of these compounds are often sufficiently long-lived to become engaged in energy transfer reactions. Their electroluminescent properties have been applied in solar energy converters² and as electroluminescent materials in OLED-type devices³. The compounds have been used as luminescent probes for long-range electron-transfer studies in proteins and other biomolecular systems⁴, and light-emitting electronic devices⁵.

Transition metals catalyze a series of biological oxidation events including hydroxylation, epoxidation, dehalogenation, sulfoxidation, dehydrogenation, alcohol and aldehyde oxidations⁶. They also play important roles in the oxidative processes employed in chemical industry and laboratory synthesis⁷. Although the categories of the oxidation reactions may change from substrate to substrate, the late transition metal oxo moieties ($M^{n+}=O$)

have been proposed to serve as key and active intermediates in most oxidation reactions⁸. With this view, in the past few decades there has been considerable interest in transition metal catalyzed oxidation of alcohols using oxidants such as molecular oxygen, iodosylbenzene, hydrogen peroxide, *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide and N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMO)⁹.

In the past few years we have engaged to synthesis new ruthenium carbonyl and triphenylphosphine complexes with azoimine and diimine functional ligands and to explore their catalytic activity towards oxidation of alcohols¹⁰. In continuation, herein we have synthesized and characterized new ruthenium triphenylphosphine complex with NNN donor Schiff base ligand, 8-{(2'-pyridylmethylene)amino}quinoline (PMAQ). An array of spectroscopic tools abetted with DFT calculation has been used to characterize the complex and to interpret the electronic structure. The catalytic activity of the complex for the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to the respective aldehyde and ketones has been studied using N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMO) as oxidizing agent.

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Experimental

Materials :

8-{(2'-Pyridylmethylene)amino}quinoline (PMAQ) was prepared following the published procedure¹¹. Ru(PPh₃)₃Cl₂, pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and 8-aminoquinoline were purchased from Aldrich, and used as received. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer CHN-2400 elemental analyzer. The electronic spectra were measured on Lambda 750 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in acetonitrile solution. The IR spectra were recorded on RX-1 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the spectral range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ with the samples in the form of KBr pellets. Luminescence property was measured using LS-55 Perkin-Elmer fluorescence spectrophotometer at room temperature (298 K) in acetonitrile solution by 1 cm path length quartz cell. Fluorescence lifetimes were measured using a time-resolved-spectrofluorometer from IBH, UK. The instrument uses a picoseconds diode laser (NanoLed-03, 370 nm) as the excitation source and works on the principle of time-correlated single photon counting¹². The goodness of fit was evaluated by χ^2 criterion and visual inspection of the residuals of the fitted function to the data. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometers in presence of TMS as internal standard. Cyclic voltammetric measurements were carried out using a CH1 Electrochemical work station. A platinum wire working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode were used in a standard three-electrode configuration. [nBu₄N][ClO₄] was used as the supporting electrolyte and the scan rate used was 50 mV s⁻¹ in acetonitrile under argon atmosphere.

The luminescence quantum yield was determined using carbazole as reference with a known ϕ_R of 0.42 in MeCN. The complex and the reference dye were excited at the same wavelength, maintaining nearly equal absorbance (~0.1), and the emission spectra were recorded. The area of the emission spectrum was integrated using the software available in the instrument and the quantum yield is calculated according to the following equation :

$$\phi_S/\phi_R = [A_S/A_R] \times [(Abs)_R/(Abs)_S] \times [\eta_S^2/\eta_R^2]$$

Here, ϕ_S and ϕ_R are the luminescence quantum yield of the sample and reference, respectively. A_S and A_R are the area under the emission spectra of the sample and the reference respectively, $(Abs)_S$ and $(Abs)_R$ are the respective optical densities of the sample and the reference solution at the wavelength of excitation, and η_S and η_R are the values of refractive index for the respective solvent used for the sample and reference.

Synthesis of *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (1) :

To a suspension of Ru(PPh₃)₃Cl₂ (192 mg, 0.2 mmol) in acetonitrile (30 mL) PMAQ (47 mg, 0.2 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 h under N₂ atmosphere. The color of the solution changed from orange to red. The solution was filtered and kept for slow evaporation of the solvent. The red crystalline compound obtained after evaporation of solvent was thoroughly washed with n-hexane. The yield was 101 mg (76%).

Anal. Calcd. for C₃₃H₂₆Cl₂N₃PRu : C, 59.38; H, 3.93; N, 6.29%. Found : C, 59.17; H, 3.86; N, 6.19%; IR data (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1591, 1530 (C=N); ¹H NMR data (DMSO-*d*₆, ppm) : 9.12 (1H, s), 8.85 (1H, d, *J* 4.05), 8.74 (1H, d, *J* 4.20), 8.12–8.21 (2H, m), 7.91 (1H, t, *J* 7.66), 7.15–7.79 (21H, m); ESI-mass in acetonitrile : *m/z*, [M + Na]⁺ = 690.19; λ_{max} (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) in acetonitrile : 524 (1967), 331 (10654), 265 (57603); $E_{1/2}$ (Ru^{II}/Ru^{III}) : 1.19 V (ΔE = 180 mV); E_{pc} : -1.17 V.

Procedure for catalytic oxidation of alcohols :

Catalytic oxidation of primary alcohols to corresponding aldehydes and secondary alcohols to ketones by ruthenium complex, *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (1) was studied in the presence of NMO as co-oxidant. A typical reaction using the complex as a catalyst and primary or secondary alcohol, as substrate at 1 : 100 molar ratio was described as follows. The solution of complex 1 (0.01 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (25 mL) was added to the mixture containing PhCH₂OH (1 mmol), NMO (3 mmol) and molecular sieves. The reaction mixture was refluxed and conversion of PhCH₂OH to PhCHO was monitored taking the reaction mixture at 10 min time interval. The solvent of the reaction mixture was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was then extracted with diethyl ether, concentrated to ≈1 mL. Conversions were determined by GC instrument equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) using a HP-5 column of 30 m

length, 0.53 mm diameter and 5.00 μm film thickness. The column, injector and detector temperatures were 200, 250 and 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ respectively. The carrier gas was N_2 (UHP grade) at a flow rate of 30 mL/min. The injection volume of sample was 2 mL. The oxidation products were identified by GC co-injection with authentic samples. No significant conversion was observed after 120 min. All other alcohols were oxidized by refluxing the reaction mixture for 2 h and conversions were monitored following the identical protocol.

Computational details :

Full geometry optimization was carried out using the density functional theory method at the B3LYP level¹³. All elements except ruthenium were assigned the 6-31G(d) basis set. The LanL2DZ basis set with effective core potential was employed for the ruthenium atom¹⁴. The vibrational frequency calculation was performed to ensure that the optimized geometry represents the local minima and there are only positive eigenvalues. All calculations were performed with Gaussian09 program package¹⁵ with the aid of the Gauss View, Version 5 visualization program. Vertical electronic excitations based on B3LYP optimized geometry were computed using the time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) formalism¹⁶ in acetonitrile using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)¹⁷. GaussSum¹⁸ was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and spectral characterization :

The ligand, 8- $\{(2'$ -pyridylmethylene)amino $\}$ quinoline (PMAQ) has been synthesized by condensation of 8-

aminoquinoline and pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde following the published procedure¹¹. The complex, *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (**1**) has been synthesized by the reaction of PMAQ with Ru(PPh₃)₃Cl₂ in acetonitrile under refluxing condition in N_2 atmosphere (Scheme 1). The complex has been characterized by several spectroscopic techniques. The ESI mass and elemental analysis supports the composition of the complex (see Experimental section). The binding of PMAQ has been proposed from ¹H NMR analysis. The significant downfield shifting of ¹H NMR signals of protons adjacent to quinoline-N and pyridyl-N of quinoline and pyridyl moieties of the ligand support the coordination of quinoline-N and pyridyl-N to ruthenium centre. Again, the signal corresponds to imine proton has been observed in downfield region compare to the free ligand value supporting the binding of imine-N. The binding of imine-N again well supported by decreasing of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching by $\sim 30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ compare to free ligand value (see Experimental section). So, the ligand PMAQ act as N,N,N donor chelator in the present complex.

The electronic spectrum of complex **1** has been taken in acetonitrile solution. A weak low energy band at 524 nm ($\epsilon = 1967\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) along with moderately intense bands at 331 nm ($\epsilon = 10654\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and strong band at 265 nm ($\epsilon = 10654\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) have been observed (Fig. 1). Upon excitation at 331 nm an emission band at 475 nm has been observed in acetonitrile with emission quantum yield, $\phi = 0.012$ (Fig. 2). Lifetime data of the compound has been taken at 298 K in acetonitrile solution when excited at 370 nm. The emission decay curve was deconvoluted with respect to the lamp profile. The observed emission decay fits with bi-exponential nature

Scheme 1. Synthesis of *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (**1**).

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectrum of complex **1** in acetonitrile.

Fig. 2. Emission spectrum of **1** in acetonitrile ($\lambda_{\text{Excitation}} = 331$ nm).

(Fig. 3). We have used mean emission lifetime ($\tau_{\text{av}} = a_1\tau_1 + a_2\tau_2$, where a_1 and a_2 are relative amplitude of decay process) to study the excited state stability of the complex. The emission lifetime of the complex is 3.98 ns.

DFT computation and electronic structure :

To get detailed insight into the electronic structure of *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (**1**), DFT calculations have been performed using DFT/B3LYP method. The optimized structure of **1** is shown in Fig. 4. Calculated selective bond distances are summarized in figure caption. The calculated Ru-N(imine) bond distance is shorter by ~ 0.1 Å compare to Ru-N(pyridyl) and Ru-N(quinoline) bond distances supporting $d\pi(\text{Ru}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{C}=\text{N})$ back donation in the complex.

The energies along with compositions of some selected

Fig. 3. Emission decay profile of **1** in acetonitrile ($\lambda_{\text{Excitation}} = 270$ nm).

Fig. 4. Optimized structure of *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (**1**) (Selected bond distances : Ru1-N1, 2.100 Å; Ru1-N2, 1.989 Å; Ru1-N3, 2.097 Å, Ru1-Cl1, 2.499 Å; Ru1-Cl2, 2.471 Å and Ru1-P1, 2.415 Å).

molecular orbitals are given in Table 1 for the complex. The HOMO, HOMO-1 and HOMO-2 have major contribution of $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbitals (46–63%) along with significant contribution of $p\pi(\text{Cl})$ (29–42%) orbitals (Fig. 5). HOMO-3 to HOMO-10 have mixed composition of $p\pi(\text{Cl})$, $\pi(\text{PMAQ})$ and $\pi(\text{PPh}_3)$ orbitals along with reduced contribution of $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbitals. The LUMO has 87% $\pi^*(\text{PMAQ})$ character with significant contribution of imine function along with reduced contribution of $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbitals. The HOMO-LUMO energy gap in the complex is 2.24 eV. The LUMO+1 to LUMO+3 exclusively have $\pi^*(\text{PMAQ})$ character except 18% contribution of PPh₃ in LUMO+2.

Table 1. Energy and composition of selected molecular orbitals of complex **1**

MO	Energy (eV)	Composition (%)			
		Ru	PMAQ	Cl	PPh ₃
LUMO+5	-0.71	01	08	0	91
LUMO+4	-0.80	14	17	04	65
LUMO+3	-0.91	03	91	0	06
LUMO+2	-0.92	03	78	01	18
LUMO+1	-1.72	04	94	01	01
LUMO	-2.64	10	87	01	02
HOMO	-4.88	49	12	36	03
HOMO-1	-4.98	63	07	29	01
HOMO-2	-5.06	46	10	42	02
HOMO-3	-5.38	02	01	93	04
HOMO-4	-5.92	18	29	49	04
HOMO-5	-6.14	20	13	43	24
HOMO-6	-6.52	17	04	36	43
HOMO-7	-6.59	10	06	21	63
HOMO-8	-6.63	10	48	18	24
HOMO-9	-6.71	01	03	02	94
HOMO-10	-6.79	12	09	23	56

TDDFT calculation and electronic spectra :

The electronic spectrum of complex **1** in acetonitrile shows a weak low energy band at 524 nm ($\epsilon = 1967$

$M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) along with moderately intense bands at 331 nm ($\epsilon = 10654 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) and strong band at 265 nm ($\epsilon = 10654 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$).

To get detailed insight into the electronic transitions of the complexes TDDFT calculation on the optimized geometries of **1** has been performed in acetonitrile. Some selected calculated vertical electronic transitions are summarized in Table 2. The HOMO→LUMO transition at 731 nm with very weak oscillator strength (f) has not been resolved in the experimental spectrum of the complex. The experimentally observed low energy broad band at 524 nm has mixed MLCT ($d\pi(Ru) \rightarrow \pi^*(PMAQ)$) and XLCT (halogen to ligand charge transfer) ($p\pi(Cl) \rightarrow \pi^*(PMAQ)$) character corresponds to HOMO-1→LUMO transition at 531 nm ($f = 0.0431$). The bands at 331 nm and 265 nm correspond to $\pi(PMAQ) \rightarrow \pi^*(PMAQ)$ (ILCT) and $\pi(PPh_3) \rightarrow \pi^*(PMAQ)$ (ILCT) transitions in the complex.

Electrochemistry :

The electrochemical behavior of the complex is investigated by cyclic voltammetry (CV) in presence of [NBu₄][ClO₄] in MeCN at scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹. The ruthenium(II) complex shows one quasi-reversible oxidative couple at 1.19 V ($\Delta E = 180$ mV) and a reductive

Fig. 5. Contour plots of selected molecular orbitals of **1**.

Table 2. Some selected singlet-singlet vertical excitations calculated by TDDFT/CPCM method for **1**

$E_{\text{Excitation}}$ (eV)	$\lambda_{\text{Excitation}}$ (nm)	Osc. strength (f)	Key transitions	Character	$\lambda_{\text{Expt.}}$ (nm) (ϵ , $M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)
1.6967	730.7	0.0140	(75%)HOMO→LUMO	$d\pi(\text{Ru})/p\pi(\text{Cl}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{PMAQ})$ (MLCT/XLCT)	
2.3331	531.4	0.0431	(77%)HOMO-1→LUMO	$d\pi(\text{Ru})/p\pi(\text{Cl}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{PMAQ})$ (MLCT/XLCT)	524 (1967)
3.7079	334.4	0.0890	(66%)HOMO-8→LUMO	$\pi(\text{PMAQ}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{PMAQ})$ (ILCT)	331 (10654)
4.3442	285.4	0.1189	(49%)HOMO-7→LUMO+1 (23%)HOMO-8→LUMO	$\pi(\text{PPh}_3/\text{PMAQ}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{PMAQ})$ (ILCT)	265 (57603)

response at -1.17 V, positive and negative to reference electrode respectively (Ag/AgCl) in the potential window 1.5 to -1.5 V. The HOMO of the complex has 49% $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ character, so the oxidation in the complex correspond to the removal of an electron from $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbital and has been assigned as Ru^{II} to Ru^{III} oxidation. The LUMO of the complex has major contribution of π^* orbital of imine function ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) of PMAQ and hence reduction has been assigned as $[\text{C}=\text{N}] \rightarrow [\text{C}=\text{N}]^{\cdot-}$ process.

Catalytic oxidation :

Catalytic oxidations of benzyl alcohol, 2-butanol, 1-phenylethanol, cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol, cycloheptanol and cycloctanol have been carried out using complex **1** as catalyst and N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMO) as oxidant in CH_2Cl_2 in refluxing condition for an appropriate period of time. The complex catalyzes the oxidation of benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde, 2-butanol to 2-butanone, 1-phenylethanol to acetophenone, cyclopentanol to cyclopentanone, cyclohexanol to cyclohexanone, cycloheptanol to cycloheptanone and cycloctanol to cycloctanone with moderate conversions and the results are given in Table 3. Series of reactions have been carried out taking either the ruthenium complex or NMO only. It has been observed that neither the ruthenium complex (**1**) nor NMO alone causes this oxidation of alcohols under identical conditions. Results of the investigations suggest that the ruthenium complex efficiently reacts with NMO to yield a high valent ruthenium-oxo species¹⁹, which is capable of oxygen atom transfer to alcohols. This was further supported by the appearance of new stretching band at 852 cm^{-1} , characteristic of $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ species in the IR spectrum²⁰.

Table 3. Catalytic oxidation of alcohols by Ru^{II} complex **1** using NMO as co-oxidant

Substrate	Product	Conversion (%) ^a
Benzyl alcohol	Benzaldehyde	69
2-Butanol	2-Butanone	65
1-Phenylethanol	Acetophenone	74
Cyclopentanol	Cyclopentanone	78
Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	75
Cycloheptanol	Cycloheptanone	77
Cycloctanol	Cycloctanone	75

^aSubstrate (1 mmol); NMO (3 mmol); complex (0.01 mmol); solvent dichloromethane; Conversions determined by GC instrument equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) using a HP-5 column of 30 m length, 0.53 mm diameter and 5.00 mm film thickness.

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammogram of **1** in acetonitrile.

Conclusion

The *cis*-(Cl)-[Ru(PMAQ)(PPh₃)Cl₂] (**1**) (where, PMAQ = 8-{(2'-pyridylmethylene)amino}quinoline) has been synthesized and characterized. The ruthenium complex efficiently catalyzes the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to the respective aldehydes and ketones with moderate to high conversions in presence of N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMO) as co-oxidant. The complex exhibits a quasi-reversible one electron $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}/$

Ru^{III} oxidation couple along with a ligand based reduction in cyclic voltammetric study. The redox properties are well supported by DFT data. The electronic structure of the complex has been interpreted by DFT computational method. The spin allowed electronic transitions computed by TDDFT method have a good agreement with the experimental spectra for the complex.

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